

FORMING YOUTH LEGAL LITERACY PROCESSES

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Abstract: Raising legal literacy of children in the family, legal consciousness and knowledge the level of development and their identification based on socio-legal activity possible. This article examines the legal literacy of the population in our society increase the newly developed law, introducing them to the decisions and measures to ensure their participation in these projects and written about additional offers.

Key words: Society, Legal consciousness, Legal education, Law, Law, Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It is known that there are rapid changes in every aspect of society in our country in the field of law, new normative-legal documents are being developed output is also accelerating. The main reason for this is legal in today's fast-paced era knowledge is increasing. Also legal literacy of the population a number of things are being done to increase it. For example, the Republic of Uzbekistan The President's Decree No. PF-5618 dated 09.01.2019 is proof of this. In Article 10 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: Every person, his determination of rights and duties and the extent of the criminal charge against him to determine whether it is justified, on the basis of complete equality, transparently, considered by an independent and impartial court, observing all the requirements of justice it is stated that he has the right to exit. On January 4, 2001, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Uzbekistan The decree "On externalizing the study of the Constitution of the Republic" on the basis of "Uzbekistan "Study of the Constitution" educational course was introduced. This training course It is considered an important component of the Constitutional law of Uzbekistan It is important to study the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in continuous education becomes important. The Constitution is the main law of the state, in which the state sovereignty, human rights and freedoms, what are their duties, what is a person what rights they have, how they are guaranteed, like state power The listener should learn to answer important questions. Also, not only the study of constitutional rights, but such to study the compatibility of rules with life, in our national legislation the extent to which the constitutional provisions are guaranteed It is scientific by comparing step by step (from simple to complex). bringing it to the level of approach is a very urgent issue. After all, legal, The very

idea of democracy requires a critical, scientific approach to law is enough. A person who has acquired legal knowledge should be able to use and apply his knowledge in life need In the course of the lesson on the rights, freedoms and duties of people and citizens to be able to use what you have learned in life, to protect yourself on the basis of the law what he does, how he fulfills his duties comes from his own actions. Legal education and training are interconnected, individual, relational and dialectic has a character and is a guarantee of forming the legal culture of an individual. After all, legal education is to provide students with systematic knowledge about the essence of legal norms, laws, and socio-legal relations, in which creating the need to acquire legal knowledge, legal consciousness is a formation process, and it should be organized in a consistent, continuous, systematic manner. Legal education is theoretical and legal knowledge acquired by a person on the basis of formation of skills and competences in the organization of legal activity to do, to find positive legal qualities in it, and legal is a pedagogical process aimed at the formation of culture. Person formation of legal culture is important in the process of legal education and upbringing stage. Legal literacy in legal literature although there is no unanimous definition of the concept, the following concept is among them can be formed: legal literacy - terms in legal texts understand, draw general conclusions from them and apply this knowledge in practice ability to receive. Foreign legal literature has a similar content represents, that is, a person's knowledge of his rights and obligations, which cases knowing that it is a legal dispute and being able to find a legal solution to them, legal where to find information, where and how to get legal help, to know what measures are available in the legal system and the procedural order are signs of legal literacy. International democratic society based on high legal culture there are widely recognized principles. Equality, liberty, fraternity, nations and international friendship, free expression of one's will and it implementation, subordination of the minority to the majority, equality of all citizens legality, election of key state agencies, their accountability to voters giving, rule of law in state and society management, by appointment the responsibility of the forming state agencies to the electoral organizations and others include

CONCLUSION. Building a democratic legal state of Uzbekistan and a fair civil society going boldly on the path of formation, a strong place in the world community occupying Because of stability and order, inter-ethnic harmony and civil harmony our young country is gaining trust and respect. Republic of Uzbekistan specific political reforms, as they mark the perspective and path of their own development and certain political, social, and economic changes as a result of it it's natural to hold.

Today, Uzbekistan is a democratic legal state to a civil society is doing a lot of important work on the way to the transition. The main purpose of this the rights and freedoms and duties of not only young people, but also all citizens of Uzbekistan as well as understanding his obligations and being able to apply them correctly in practice among others, from raising the political capacity in managing state power, it is assumed that he will occupy a worthy place in society. There is a lot of our country development and the success of the reforms are largely due to the people's legal system depends on the level of consciousness and legal culture. Political activity of the person, his a truly civil attitude, a desire for democratic reforms is defined is an important factor in achieving goals. High legal culture is democratic it is the foundation of the society and the expression of maturity of the legal system.

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